

INDUCTIVE WAY OF TEACHING VOCABULARY USING COLLAGATIONS

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Annotation: This thesis analyzes the utilize of inductive vocabularies in instructing lexicon with the assistance of collogations. When a word that's an component of a field is utilized by a speaker or gotten by a audience, it is encompassed by other words in that field, a complete picture of that word. for us to make, not a single word is cleared out out of the field. Each word taken independently is justifiable as it were as a entirety, and as it were on the premise of this complex can the meaning of the word be caught on.

Key words: Dictionary, phenomena and events, vocabularies in the form of pictures, development of thinking, expressions of concepts and actions.

It is known that there are two ways to portray the lexicon of a language, i.e. "from frame to meaning" and "from meaning to create". When taking after the primary path, the errand of the describer is to grant the foremost accurate and total portrayal of the word, its particular employments and implications. Within the moment method, on the opposite, the strategies of rise of the existing substance and implications of the concept within the dialect are lit up one by one. These two headings are similarly vital in etymology and in instruction.

Etymologists chose the primary strategy within the creation of all word references distributed within the Uzbek dialect. We continuously turn to these word references when learning a outside dialect, and in most cases, when we come over an new word or sentence in our possess dialect. But there are too cases when we know what we need to say and cannot discover the proper words to precise our contemplations. It is in such circumstances that an ideographic lexicon would have been useful to us. Since the most reason of the ideographic lexicon is to supply viable offer assistance in choosing the word essential to specific a certain thought. Maybe that's why, for a century and a half, genuine significance has been joined to the creation of word references of this sort in Europe. An illustration of this can be Mark Peter Roger's "Thesaurus of English Words and Phrases" (1852), which is recognized as the primary ideographic word reference, and a number of comparative lexicons in Spanish, German, French, and other dialects that taken after..

So what may be a word reference? Is there any association between "lexicon" and the already known term "ideographic composing" in etymology, or are the words "ideographic" in these terms fair irregular homonyms? We know from the history of phonetics that in old times, individuals accomplished the objective of passing on or immortalizing a few occasions and occasions to long separations by drawing pictures of quicken and lifeless objects in nature.

These pictorial works or shapes are called pictographs in phonetics. (Pictus implies "drawn" in Latin, and the word "grapho" implies "to type in" in Greek). Within the improvement of society, pictographic composing steadily moved forward, from the appearance of pictures to

the appearance of shapes, but through pictograms, as it were concrete things in nature can be reflected, seen by the eye and held by the hand. This writing was not able to precise concepts and implications that were not accessible. As a result of the advancement and advancement of people's intellect and considering, in contrast to the pictographic composing, the "composing of concepts", that's, the ideographic composing, was made. In this, expressions of unique concepts and activities were made by combining the images of living and lifeless objects.

For illustration, the shape speaking to the meaning of "mouth" and the shape meaning "puppy" are compared, and the meaning of "bark" is uncovered, the images "mouth" and "fowl" are not "singing". title, "eye" and "tree" cruel "to see", the images "moon" and "sun" cruel "light", the combined shape of two palms implies "fellowship" spoken to the nose. In expansion to their unique meaning, a few images were moreover utilized in metaphorical implications. For case, the image "eye" is additionally utilized within the meaning of "eye sharpness".

In this case, the utilize of the image in a strict or metaphorical sense is decided by its environment.

This wonder is comparable to the method of arrangement of versatile meaning by means of metonymy within the vocabulary, that's, the title of the question is exchanged to the title of its item: "tongue" - the organ of the verbal depression, "tongue" - human capacity to talk; "eye" - the organ of vision, "eye" - sharp visual perception. So, ideographic composing was made on the premise of endeavors to specific the concept, and it is decided by the crave of individuals to reflect their thoughts and considerations in composing. At this point, we found it essential to pay consideration to the meaning of the word ideographic: "The thought is Greek. A concept, creative ability that reflects the objective presence, reality within the intellect of a individual, communicates the state of mind of a individual to the objective presence, reality, and shapes the premise of people's world sees.

The word "grafo" implies "to type in", as we said over. In spite of the fact that M. Roger named his word reference based on otherworldly standards "Thesaurus", this asset is additionally called "ideographic lexicon" in phonetics, since it is focused on clarifying concepts instead of words. So, within the ideographic dictionary, not the words, but the concepts they cruel are reflected in conjunction with their environment in our intellect and creative ability based on their otherworldly association with existing things and occasions. In this case, the meaning of the word is revealed not by giving it a definition, but by interfacing it with other lexical bunches and ideas, comparing and comparing it. Subsequently, within the ideographic word reference, words are set not in in sequential order arrange, but on the premise of their otherworldly standards, that's, joined together in topical bunches.

In Europe, the ideographic word reference was moreover called a thesaurus after M. Roger. The word "thesaurus" implies treasure in Greek. In etymology, this term, in expansion to its fundamental meaning, is utilized in two other implications: the primary implies "the foremost culminate word reference", and the moment meaning is distant from the field of etymology and alludes to the human capacity to know. speaks to a total set. Consequently, consistent systematic research in the field of semasiology serves as an

important supporting factor in the creation of such dictionaries and "relieves the lexicographer from the difficulties of organizing and introducing and interpreting meaningless speech meanings into dictionaries."

The famous Russian linguist L.V. Sherba, in his article on the theory of lexicography, shows six types of comparisons within different dictionaries, and interprets thesauruses and dictionaries as separate forms of dictionaries. According to the scientist, the peculiarity of the thesaurus is that they mention all the words of a certain language, even the least used ones, even those that occur even once in speech, and each word below are quotations from various texts available in this language to illustrate it.

The scientist evaluates ordinary (i.e. usual) dictionaries as a "phonetic word list", while ideological (i.e. ideographic) dictionaries are a list of words and their synonyms. evaluates.

In the "Dictionary of Linguistic Terms" by O.S. Akhmanova, it is noted that "in ideological dictionaries, words are placed on the basis of subject lines." Many scientists include both types of dictionaries in one series due to the fact that they have certain commonalities.

The theoretical ideas of ideographic dictionaries are associated with the name of the German scientist Y.Trier. He brought the concept of semantic field to linguistics and developed its theoretical and practical aspects. According to Trier's definition, a given word is intelligible only with the help of its surroundings, which form a whole field. If the listener does not have an adequate idea of the field associated with the word and of those who conflict with the word within that field, or if the listener has completely different concepts around the word, then the spoken word will have no meaning; and as it is applied to the real field, the boundaries of the used word will be clarified and clarified.

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